

Article

Application of Magnetometer-Equipped Drone for Mineral Exploration in Mining Operations

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Abstract: This study investigates the geological composition and material distribution within the Lavrion repository located in Greece through an aerial magnetometry survey using a novel aerial drone, CERBERUS, coupled with advanced data processing techniques. The deployment of drone-based magnetometry provided a high-resolution, non-invasive approach to capturing magnetic field data over complex and potentially hazardous terrain (soils highly contaminated), facilitating the rapid and precise mapping of the study area. As a final result, a 3D magnetic susceptibility model was developed, representing a detailed view of the magnetic susceptibility variations within the repository. This model enabled the comprehensive visualization of high-susceptibility zones associated with ferromagnetic materials and low-susceptibility zones correlating with diamagnetic materials like lead, arsenic, cadmium, and zinc. The combined methodologies underscore the effectiveness of drone-based aerial magnetometry in geophysical studies, highlighting its potential for mining exploration and waste management. This study demonstrates that the integration of drone technology with magnetic data processing offers a powerful tool for analysing subsurface structures in a safe, efficient, and non-invasive manner.

Keywords: mining; exploration; waste management; drone; magnetometer; 3D inversion models

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1. Introduction

The mining industry is growing at an unprecedented rate due to increasing mineral demand, especially for metals that support the current energy transition. Over the past decades, this industry has had to face different challenges to improve productivity and meet the current demand. Decreasing ore grades and the existence of deeper deposits and harder rock formations, coupled with social and environmental awareness, has pushed mining activity to constantly work and adapt to these new conditions [1,2].

Despite the clear and growing need for mineral exploration and extraction, many actors of the mining industry claim that the sector is still at the early stages of the change demanded by the global digital transformation. However, the changes and innovations introduced in each of the stages that a mining operation encompasses are notable, denoting that technological advances play and will play an essential role in the future development of the mining industry [3,4].

Regarding one of the most decisive phases of the mining operation, the exploration, it is considered a complex process that requires the development of a data collection and conceptualization protocol capable of effectively delineating areas of interest within a

certain deposit. In this context, the recent development of small-scale Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) equipped with sensors of different natures has created a powerful tool for spatial mapping and exploring [5,6]. Although the most popular applications of drones are associated with the acquisition and processing of aerial images, the miniaturization of geophysical sensors has opened new opportunities for their on-board installation. Examples of these developments in underground surveys are the implementation of UAV-borne ground-penetrating radar [7,8], drone-mounted magnetometers [9–12], or the use of UAVs equipped with Light Detection and Ranging (LiDAR) sensors for underwater prospecting purposes [13]. These combinations are especially important when the extension of the areas to be explored is too large or their access is not viable to carry out the traditional prospecting method.

Focusing on magnetic methods, one of the most effective techniques for mineral exploration, these surveys are traditionally performed on-site, moving the sensor manually and collecting high-resolution spatial data at the cost of very low productivity [14–17]. In fact, despite the information about the magnetic field being provided with a very high spatial resolution, the device requires to be carried along all the profiles, this being a complex task in difficult terrains such as rocks or swamps [18]. This is why the incorporation of drones in this field offers multiple advantages, such as lower logistics costs, flexibility, and ease of use. In fact, magnetometers mounted on UAVs allow combining the advantages of the shooting speed and area coverage of a drone with a resolution comparable to conventional ground-based systems [19].

Given the importance of extending the use of these advanced aerial prospecting methodologies in the mining field, this research focuses on exploring the potential of using a drone-based magnetometer for the exploration of a certain historic mining site. To this end, an innovative UAV device has been developed to incorporate a magnetometer sensor, taking into consideration the possible operational limitations, such as the size and weight of the sensor, the distance between the drone and the magnetic receiver, or different factors associated with the flight conditions. In addition to this new technological development, this research is developed in a relevant mining context where the possible identification of potential minerals is presented as one of the key points for the rehabilitation of mining enclaves and effective metal recovery. Based on this, the paper is structured as follows. First, a description of the geological and global conditions of the site under study is provided in Section 2. A methodological section describing the integrated magnetometer-UAV used for the prospecting surveys and the data collection and processing is detailed in Section 3. The main results of the geophysical campaigns are outlined in Section 4. A conclusion section is devoted to highlighting the principal findings of the implementation of the method in the particular mining context.

2. Geological Context of the Lavrion District

Lavrion is located at the southernmost tip of the Attica Peninsula in southern Greece, approximately 60 km southeast of the country's capital city, Athens. It is one of the oldest mining areas in the world, with mining activities recorded since the second millennium BC. Mining and smelting metallurgical activities continued, even with numerous interruptions, until the end of World War II, after which they eventually ceased in the 1970s [20].

The Lavrion district, which belongs to the Attic–Cycladic crystalline belt, consists of three main tectonic units of Alpine age (Figure 1a): the Kamariza unit (or Lower tectonic unit), the Lavrion blueschist (or Middle tectonic unit), and the Berzekos unit (or Upper tectonic unit) [21]. The basal Kamariza unit is composed of two marble layers of Late Triassic to Early Jurassic age, namely the Upper and Lower marble, as well as the so-called Kamariza schists. The Lavrion unit, which is of Late Jurassic to Cretaceous age, structurally

overlies the Kamariza unit and consists of the Lavrion schist, marbles, and a meta-ophiolite. The Upper Cycladic unit has limited exposure and comprises Upper Cretaceous micritic limestone [22].

Figure 1. Geological overview: (a) Simplified geological map of the Lavrion ore district [22]; (b) Geological sketch map of the Plaka area [22].

Several occurrences of granite and granodiorite intrusions, such as laccoliths, pipes, dikes, and sills, are exposed across the Lavrion district. Among these, the Plaka intrusion (Figure 1b) is particularly notable; it is an I-type granodiorite surrounded by an extensive contact metamorphic aureole of calc–silicate hornfels within the Kamariza schists [23]. Along with Kamariza, Plaka is one of the most important mining areas in the Lavrion district.

A distinguishing feature of the Lavrion deposit is its five distinct but interrelated styles of mineralization. These types include (a) porphyry Mo–W, (b) Fe–Cu–Bi–Au skarn, (c) high-temperature carbonate replacement (skarn-free) Pb–Zn–Cu–Ag–Au mineralization, and (d, e) Pb–Zn–Ag–Au vein and breccia deposits [24]. With 672 documented minerals, including 25 type locality minerals, the Lavrion district hosts the highest number of distinct mineral elements of any known mining district [25]. This makes Lavrion an invaluable natural laboratory for geological, mineralogical, and geochemical research, offering scientists a nearly inexhaustible field of study and ideal opportunities for education. Furthermore, the integration of Lavrion’s mineralogical, geological, archaeological, and metallurgical sites into the UNESCO Global Geoparks network [26], ensures the preservation of its geological and cultural heritage, promotes educational activities, and supports sustainable development.

3. Materials and Methods

3.1. Drone Platform

The successful development of a customized UAV requires a diligent and well-structured approach to material selection and design methods that align with the overarching goals of adaptability and versatility. This section outlines the operational objectives of the UAV. The methodology used in both the conceptual and detailed design phases

was closely followed, as outlined by Perikleous et al. [27]. The integration of cutting-edge technologies and careful consideration of materials are crucial to the UAV's ability to dynamically adapt its form and function.

3.1.1. Operational Objectives

Durability Objectives

The CERBERUS UAV is capable of taking off from and landing on various types of terrain, including gravel, dirt, grass, and snow, thanks to its landing gear. It is anticipated to withstand winds of up to 6 Beaufort scale (6 bft) speed and maintain its position. The drone's flight duration depends on the payload; however, it typically offers an average flight time of 35–40 min.

Performance Objectives

The total take-off weight of the drone, including the attached payload, has been calculated to be below 25 kg, in accordance with the A3 open category under EASA drone regulations [28]. The UAV is designed to follow the general rule that the maximum thrust per motor must be at least twice the hovering thrust force. Ensuring compliance with this rule enhances safety by providing a power reserve for use in adverse conditions or unexpected events, such as strong winds or manoeuvres. More specifically, the total weight of the drone, including the payload, is 10.5 kg, while the overall maximum thrust of the motors is 22.8 kg. Thus, more than 50% of the total thrust is available for flight.

Design Objectives

The dimensions of the UAV have been calculated with consideration to the optimal gap distance between the rotors, which suggests that the space between propellers should be around 18% of the propeller diameter [29]. By designing the UAV's dimensions based on this calculation, we aimed to optimize its performance while ensuring safe and reliable operation during flight. The drone has the minimum possible dimensions necessary to host all the necessary equipment. Its external diameter (distance between two opposite motors) is 1.25 m and it is dependent on the size of the propellers, which in our case have a length of approximately 40 cm.

Technological Objectives

The prototype includes basic drone status control technologies, such as power level monitoring, battery status, and WiFi antenna communication, alongside more advanced flight and communication features. Specifically, during operation, it can manage and monitor basic flight statuses such as take-off, flight, and landing, as well as execute predefined autonomous flight scenarios. Additionally, a companion computer is available for integration on the UAV if required.

Regarding GPS, the UAV employed in the present work demands high-precision geolocation. To meet this requirement, the H-RTK F9P, a high-precision GNSS positioning system series from Holybro (Holybro, Hong Kong, China), has been utilised. This system supports multi-band RTK with fast convergence times and reliable performance. It enables the concurrent reception of GPS (L1C/A and L2C), GLONASS (L1OF and L2OF), Galileo (E1-B/C and E5b), and BeiDou (B2a) signals and features a rapid update rate, making it suitable for highly dynamic and high-volume applications requiring centimetre-level accuracy.

3.1.2. Drone Layout Design and Prototype

In presenting the drone layout design, the authors leverage SOLIDWORKS 2024, a prominent computer-aided design (CAD) and computer-aided engineering (CAE) software program widely employed by engineers globally. This powerful tool facilitated the creation

of a comprehensive and detailed 3D design, serving as the cornerstone for the developed innovative drone architecture.

Frame

The drone frame consists mainly of two flat carbon fibre sheets (Figure 2a) and four arm mounts (Figure 2b), which also serve as structural parts of the frame. Aluminium spacers have been incorporated at key points to increase structural stiffness. Slots and holes have also been included to facilitate the installation of all the components and cable routing. Finally, all electronic components of the UAV are enclosed within a custom Carbon Fiber-Reinforced Plastic (CFRP) cover (Figure 2c) to enhance the safety of the internal components.

Figure 2. UAV 3D designs. (a) UAV frame; (b) arm mount; (c) UAV cover.

The drawings in Figure 2 were extracted for manufacturing on a CNC cutting machine. The CFRP cover was formed with a moulding process and high temperature-cured in a vacuum (vacuum bagging). The resulting output is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Manufactured UAV frame.

Arms with Motors and Propellers

The drone's frame features four arms, each equipped with a Y-type joint designed to support two motor-propeller pairs on each arm, as shown in Figure 4. This configuration enables the frame to host a total of eight motor-propeller pairs. The arms are easily detachable to reduce the required space and facilitate the transportation/storing of the drone when not in use.

For the manufacturing of the arms, carbon tubes were cut and drilled. The Y-type joint, located at the centre of the assembly, was designed in a CAD environment and 3D printed to join the three carbon tubes.

Figure 4. Arms with motors and propellers: (a) 3D designed; (b) prototype manufactured.

The external dimensions of the CERBERUS prototype are presented below (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Frame and arms assembled: (a) 3D designed—top view; (b) manufactured—top view.

Landing Gear

The landing gear was designed to fulfil the following requirements:

- Provide a steady and impact-proof base for the drone.
- Ensure easy and safe take-off and landing operations for the drone.

The carbon tubes were cut and drilled according to the design. The joints were 3D printed and stainless-steel bolts were used to assemble them, forming the landing gear, as shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Landing gear: (a) 3D designed—trimetric view; (b) manufactured—trimetric view.

Completed Drone Assembly

Finally, all electronic components, power cables, and signal wiring were installed in their designated positions along with the sub-assemblies mentioned in the previous paragraphs. The result can be seen in Figure 7.

Figure 7. CERBERUS UAV: (a) 3D designed; (b) Manufactured.

3.1.3. System Requirements and Technical Specifications

The matrices offer a comprehensive overview, encompassing the system requirements of the UAV (Table 1) as well as the technical specifications for the UAV's configuration (Table 2).

Table 1. UAV System Requirements.

Requirements	Description
Nominal battery voltage: 22.2 V	2 × 6S LiPo batteries in parallel configuration.
Battery charger	Battery charger that can charge 2 LiPo batteries simultaneously (up to 6S).
Radio transmitter for manual piloting	Radio transmitter, compatible with the embedded autopilot, suitable for the manual piloting and monitoring of the power consumption.
Ground station	Necessary for the preparation and the execution of the flight.

Table 2. UAV Technical Specifications.

Parameters	Description
Max diameter	1.65 m
Weight (no payload)	9.5 kg
Maximum payload weight	5 kg
Expected flight time	35–40 min
Total motor thrust (100%)	22.8 Kg

The comparison of the CERBERUS prototype with widely used drones in mining applications, such as the DJI M300 [30], is inevitable. The DJI M300 has a maximum take-off weight (MTOW) of 9 kg and can carry a maximum payload of 2.7 kg, whereas CERBERUS features a larger MTOW, allowing it to carry payloads of up to 5 kg. Even when compared to drones with similar characteristics used in magnetometry applications, CERBERUS excels due to its ease of use, featuring a plug-and-play approach with modular arms and

landing gear capable of accommodating substantial payloads. This makes it particularly suitable for future geophysical applications such as Ground-Penetrating Radar (GPR) or Gamma-Ray Spectrometry (GRS).

Unlike commercialized products that prioritize ease of use, CERBERUS also offers robust features specifically tailored for research purposes. With its hardware upgradeability, the ability to accommodate an onboard processor, and its design centred around open-source flight control software, CERBERUS provides scientists and researchers with great flexibility and control.

In conclusion, CERBERUS offers a versatile solution, enabling users to customize both the drone and its software for magnetometry missions and a wide range of future geophysical applications.

3.2. Magnetometry

Magnetometer surveys consist of measuring the strength of the magnetic field on the Earth's surface at regular intervals along a series of lines called a profile. Although a considerable percentage of the geomagnetic field comes from the Earth's core (>90%), the distribution of different materials and especially ferromagnetic materials in the Earth's crust produce variations in the local magnetic field that can be recorded.

The CERBERUS Prototype was equipped with an ultra-light potassium magnetometer GEM GSMP-35U (sensitivity 0.0002 nT @ 1 Hz) with external GPS recording of the positioning simultaneous to the magnetic field and a measuring range from 20,000 to 120,000 nT. The magnetic sensor was deployed with no rotational restrictions about any of the axes.

The mesh and recording characteristics were as follows: profiles were laid out parallel with a maximum linear spacing of 10 m and the flight speed was maintained at 5 m/s. Data were collected at a sampling interval of 100 ms, corresponding to 10 measurements per second. A constant flight altitude relative to the ground was maintained using a high-precision digital terrain model previously generated with drone-based LiDAR technology at a spatial resolution of 10 cm. The flight platform was set at a height of 10 m, with the sensor positioned at 7 m above ground level. The flight direction was preplanned, following a NW–SE orientation. The mesh and the actual flight lines of the survey are summarised in Table 3.

Table 3. Characteristics and design of the flight area.

Area (Ha)	Separation between Lines (m)	No. Lines	Flight Speed (m/s)	Sampling Interval (ms)	Sensor Height (m)
1.9	10	12	5	100	7

These system components include a lightweight high-sensitivity magnetometer, electronic cable, and sensor electronics box with a system weight of under 1.0 kg. All the required components were securely fixed and balanced in the landing gear of the drone (Figure 8). Due to the magnetic interference that is generated by electromagnetic motors within the platform, the magnetic sensor was installed at a 3 m distance from the base of the drone, connected by cable, so as to counteract this electromagnetic effect [11,15,17,31–33]. In this configuration, the magnetic field produced by the drone is attenuated and does not affect the measurements of the GSMP-35U magnetometer. Nevertheless, various measurements of the surface magnetic field were conducted at different distances between the drone and the magnetometer to confirm that the preliminary distance of 3 m was sufficient to avoid interference in the magnetic signal. Additionally, as the CERBERUS prototype represents a new platform, the drone underwent testing at the National Technical

University of Athens. The tests included the following: (i) the first test confirmed that the drone's magnetic interference falls within acceptable limits for a commercial product; (ii) the second test verified that external magnetic interferences do not affect the drone's operation. All tests were performed with the drone operating on the same batteries used in the mining application in Lavrion, Greece. In addition, the batteries used in this study were LiPo batteries, which are primarily made of materials such as lithium salts, electrolytes, and carbon-based anodes, none of which are ferromagnetic. The outer casing of the LiPo batteries is made of plastic, which is a non-magnetic material.

Figure 8. CERBERUS UAV with the GSMP-35U magnetometer: (a) CERBERUS UAV take off; (b) Field data collection. Considering the potential impact of unfavourable weather conditions on data collection, the campaigns were conducted under optimal environmental conditions (as illustrated in Figure 8), ensuring minimal magnetometer oscillations.

Last but not least, during data acquisition, a stationary magnetometer (GSMP-35 magnetometer) was positioned in a nearby location, carefully selected to avoid sources of magnetic interference. Its purpose was to monitor and correct for the diurnal variations in the Earth's magnetic field caused by temporal changes throughout the day. The magnetometer was configured to record the total magnetic field at 1 s intervals, ensuring precise data for this correction. The magnetometer base station data was synchronized with the UAV-mounted magnetometer using a GPS clock.

3.3. Processing and Interpretation

The aim of data processing is to extract significant information from the field data for subsequent interpretation. The processing flow addresses errors in the signal that are unrelated to geology and mineralogy which may arise from factors such as the data acquisition methods, equipment used, external sources, and temporal variations. These factors can lead to the "contamination" of the recorded signal. To address these issues, a series of mathematical filters were applied to extract and present relevant information for interpretation. Initially, erroneous data related to the drone's position, including take-off, landing and turn times required to align with each flight line, were discarded. Next, the diurnal variations in the magnetic field were corrected and then the airborne quality control module of OASIS Montaj 2024.1 was used to analyse and remove possible noise in the data. During this process, the data were checked for heading errors, which were not detected.

The processing of the aeromagnetic data was carried out using an interpolation routine that organised the observed values into a regular grid. The resulting nodes were plotted on

a 2D contour map of the total magnetic field (RGB image). For this study, the minimum curvature meshing method was applied, adjusted to a resolution of one quarter of the flight line spacing (10 m), which is equivalent to a cell size of 2.5 m. Following the initial data processing, additional filtering processes are conducted to separate and extract anomalies related to specific geological, structural, mineralogical, and depth characteristics. All data treatment and processing are performed using specialized magnetic survey data processing software (GemLink 5.4 and OASIS Montaj 2024.1) As a result of all these filtering processes, the different profiles and magnetic signal models of the reservoir under study are obtained. As will be described in later sections, these preliminary data can also lead to the generation of 3D models of the reservoir through the application of specific inversion techniques [34,35]. This is done by creating a mathematical model that simulates the magnetic field response of various subsurface structures and iteratively adjusting the model to minimize the difference between observed and simulated magnetic data. In particular, we apply the Tikhonov regularization combined with least-squares inversion.

The final step involves the interpretation of the results, which is typically supported by the available information and the experience gained by the geophysicist from previous projects in similar contexts. All the set of stages and processes required are included in Figure 9.

Figure 9. Drone-based magnetometer data processing workflow.

4. Results

To facilitate the interpretation of the results from the magnetic geophysical prospecting, a brief review of material properties is provided, with reference to ferromagnetic, antiferromagnetic, paramagnetic, and diamagnetic materials. For a comprehensive discussion, readers are referred to [36,37]. Figure 10 presents a periodic table of the elements, highlighting the different types of magnetic susceptibilities, while Table 4 provides a list of metals in the repository along with their respective magnetic susceptibilities.

1 H	<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around; align-items: center;"> <div style="display: flex; flex-direction: column; gap: 5px;"> <div style="display: flex; align-items: center;"> Ferromagnetic</div> <div style="display: flex; align-items: center;"> Antiferromagnetic</div> </div> <div style="display: flex; flex-direction: column; gap: 5px;"> <div style="display: flex; align-items: center;"> Diamagnetic</div> <div style="display: flex; align-items: center;"> Paramagnetic</div> </div> </div>																2 He
3 Li	4 Be											5 B	6 C	7 N	8 O	9 F	10 Ne
11 Na	12 Mg											13 Al	14 Si	15 P	16 S	17 Cl	18 Ar
19 K	20 Ca	21 Sc	22 Ti	23 V	24 Cr	25 Mn	26 Fe	27 Co	28 Ni	29 Cu	30 Zn	31 Ga	32 Ge	33 As	34 Se	35 Br	36 Kr
37 Rb	38 Sr	39 Y	40 Zr	41 Nb	42 Mo	43 Tc	44 Ru	45 Rh	46 Pd	47 Ag	48 Cd	49 In	50 Sn	51 Sb	52 Te	53 I	54 Xe
55 Cs	56 Ba	57 La	72 Hf	73 Ta	74 W	75 Re	76 Os	77 Ir	78 Pt	79 Au	80 Hg	81 Tl	82 Pb	83 Bi	84 Po	85 At	86 Rn
87 Fr	88 Ra	89 Ac															
			58 Ce	59 Pr	60 Nd	61 Pm	62 Sm	63 Eu	64 Gd	65 Tb	66 Dy	67 Ho	68 Er	69 Tm	70 Yb	71 Lu	

Figure 10. Magnetic properties of the elements.

Table 4. Average metal and metalloid concentrations (mg kg^{-1}) in the Repository of Lavrion (Greece) and magnetic susceptibility (SI). Ferromagnetic elements such as Ni and Fe do not have specified magnetic susceptibility values due to their extremely high susceptibilities which vary significantly depending on external factors such as material composition, temperature, and structure, making them non-constant. This contrasts with diamagnetic, paramagnetic, and antiferromagnetic materials, whose susceptibility values are relatively constant and predictable under standard conditions.

Element	Average Concentration	Maximum Concentration	Magnetic Susceptibility
<i>Pb</i>	32.430	67.700	Diamagnetic −0.000017
<i>As</i>	4.517	10.800	Diamagnetic −0.0000223
<i>Cd</i>	160	600	Diamagnetic −0.0000199
<i>Cr</i>	4	10	Antiferromagnetic 0.0003177
<i>Ni</i>	150	300	Ferromagnetic
<i>Zn</i>	47.843	97.900	Diamagnetic −0.0000158
<i>Mn</i>	9.002	16.600	Paramagnetic 0.00090387
<i>Fe</i>	154.800	275.200	Ferromagnetic
<i>Cu</i>	2.548	6.300	Diamagnetic − 9.63×10^{-6}

4.1. Total Magnetic Field (TMF)

The image presented below (Figure 11) illustrates the plan with the results of the magnetic survey conducted in the study area. The data reveal notable variations in the repository materials, inferred from the magnetic field, which suggest the presence of compositionally distinct regions. However, no significant magnetic dipoles indicative of magnetic bodies were detected within the surveyed area.

The survey revealed areas with variations in magnetic intensity, which suggests differences in the composition or type of materials present in the ground. Particularly, lead (*Pb*), arsenic (*As*), cadmium (*Cd*), zinc (*Zn*), and copper (*Cu*) are the main diamagnetic elements present in this repository. Despite being present in varying concentrations, these elements likely contribute only weakly to the overall magnetic field, thus not forming any significant magnetic anomalies or dipoles. The high concentration of cadmium (160 on average, up to 600) is noteworthy; however, due to its weak diamagnetic nature, it does not produce a strong magnetic signal. Chromium (*Cr*) has a slightly positive magnetic susceptibility due to its antiferromagnetic properties. At a low concentration (average of 4, maximum of 10), chromium may produce subtle magnetic variations. Regarding ferromagnetic materials, nickel (*Ni*) and iron are ferromagnetic and therefore significantly influence magnetic field readings due to their strong positive magnetic susceptibilities. Nickel has a moderate concentration (150 average, up to 300), which can create localized magnetic anomalies. Iron (*Fe*), with a high average concentration (154.8, up to 275.2), is likely the primary contributor to magnetic variations detected in the survey. Iron's ferromagnetic properties make it highly responsive in magnetic surveys, which might explain the observed compositional variations. Despite these concentrations, the data suggest no significant dipoles, indicating an absence of concentrated metallic bodies of iron or nickel large enough to produce distinct magnetic anomalies. This implies that while iron and nickel are present, they are distributed in a dispersed manner. Regarding paramagnetic materials, manganese (*Mn*) has a relatively weak magnetic susceptibility and moderate

concentration (9 average, up to 16.6). While it may contribute subtly to the overall magnetic field, its impact is minimal in comparison to ferromagnetic materials like iron and nickel.

Figure 11. Total magnetic field (coordinate reference system—CRS: WGS84). While the data may appear smoothed, no smoothing filters were applied in this study. An analysis using the OASIS Montaj ‘airborne quality control’ module was conducted to check for heading errors and none were detected. Additionally, it is worth noting that a potassium magnetometer was employed, which is less susceptible to heading errors compared to other technologies, such as proton magnetometers [38].

4.2. Magnetic Field Reduction to the Pole (MFRP)

The pole-reduced magnetic field technique in magnetic surveying transforms surface-measured magnetic anomalies as if they were located directly over the north magnetic pole. This method removes the effects of the Earth’s magnetic field tilt and declination, enabling anomalies to be interpreted as if the magnetic field were vertical. This adjustment simplifies the identification and location of underground magnetic sources, as the resulting anomalies are symmetrical and centred over the sources, offering a clearer and more accurate representation of the distribution of magnetized bodies in the subsurface.

The Magnetic Field Reduction to Pole (MFRP) plane (Figure 12) shows minimal deviations from the Total Magnetic Field (MTF) data, with a magnetic field variation of approximately 1000 nT between the lowest and highest values. Despite this, the results still demonstrate significant variation in the magnetic field within the repository, indicating compositionally differentiable areas.

Figure 12. Total Magnetic Field Reduced to Pole (CRS: WGS84).

4.3. Analytical Signal (AS)

The analytical signal is used to highlight magnetic anomalies relative to the regional background, emphasizing deviations from the average magnetic values of the study area (Figure 13). As illustrated, the most prominent magnetic anomalies are located in the northeastern section of the repository. This suggests that this region has a relatively higher concentration of magnetic materials compared to other areas. Given the magnetic susceptibilities and concentrations of materials within the repository, iron (*Fe*) and possibly nickel (*Ni*) are likely contributing to these elevated anomalies. Their ferromagnetic properties make them more responsive in magnetic surveys and thus more detectable in the analytical signal. The distinction of this anomaly from the background indicates that, while magnetic materials may be dispersed throughout the repository, the northeastern section has a concentrated variation, possibly due to localized deposition or a specific phase in the repository’s history.

Figure 13. Analytic signal (CRS: WGS84).

4.4. TILT Derivative (TD)

The TILT derivative (Figure 14a) highlights the contact zones between bodies with distinct magnetic properties, which are associated with compositional discontinuities. The TILT derivative is designed to enhance the edges or boundaries between materials with distinct magnetic susceptibilities, effectively highlighting transitions or contact zones. These contact zones are a key objective of the research. The plan is particularly informative, as it reveals numerous linear contacts (Figure 14b), indicating the presence of materials with varying compositions within the repository. The linear contact zones suggest that the repository's materials may be organized in a stratified or segmented pattern. This could be due to different phases of deposition, intentional layering of materials, or variations in the natural composition of the repository contents.

Finally, the magnetic field values reduced to the pole were added to the TILT plane (Figure 15), enabling a more precise and detailed interpretation of the various elements present within the repository. This enhancement improves the understanding and analysis of the compositional characteristics of the study area. As shown, the repository contains different compartments with varying magnetic field values. The areas with higher magnetic field values are likely associated with regions of elevated concentrations of ferromagnetic materials, such as iron and nickel. A subsequent 3D susceptibility model will provide further refinement in the interpretation of these data.

Figure 14. (a) TILT derivative (WGS84 35N); (b) Interpretation of TILT derivative (WGS84).

Figure 15. Interpretation of the TILT derivative and Magnetic Field Reduced to Pole (CRS: WGS84).

Given the identified materials (e.g., iron, nickel, and manganese as magnetic contributors), these linear zones might reflect areas where ferromagnetic or paramagnetic materials transition to regions dominated by diamagnetic substances (like lead, zinc, and cadmium).

4.5. Pseudo Gravity (PG)

The pseudo-gravity filter (Figure 16) is a data processing technique applied in the magnetic survey of a repository that converts magnetic anomalies into simulated gravity anomalies. This conversion is based on the concept that materials within the repository, such as those with varying magnetic properties and densities, can produce anomalies in both the magnetic and gravity fields. By applying this filter, magnetic anomalies are transformed into a gravimetric representation, facilitating the identification and characterization of different zones within the waste repository. This approach enhances the understanding of the distribution and composition of the buried materials, improving the precision of site management and monitoring.

Figure 16. Pseudo gravity (CRS: WGS84).

As shown, the materials with the highest density and pseudo-gravity values are located in the central, southeastern, and northwestern parts of the repository. Given the repository's material composition, it is likely that regions with high pseudo-gravity values correlate with areas containing higher amounts of ferromagnetic materials (such as iron and nickel) and potentially other dense substances not magnetically responsive but with significant mass. The pseudo-gravity representation provides a new layer of information, especially valuable for distinguishing between materials with similar magnetic properties but different densities. This is particularly useful in complex repositories where both

magnetic susceptibility and density may vary due to diverse materials. For example, iron and nickel contribute both magnetic susceptibility and density, making them prominent in both magnetic and pseudo-gravity interpretations. However, other dense materials (e.g., possibly non-magnetic components in the waste) would stand out in pseudo-gravity but not necessarily in the magnetic data alone, thus allowing for a fuller assessment of repository contents.

4.6. 3D Inversion Model

The deployment of the CERBERUS drone has enabled the creation of a high-resolution, uniform grid, facilitating the development of three-dimensional models that depict magnetic susceptibility through advanced inversion techniques. These models, generated using VOXI Earth Modelling software from OASIS Montaj, have significantly streamlined the identification and delineation of the spatial boundaries of various magnetic bodies.

A 3D magnetic susceptibility model (Figures 17–19) has been developed using the magnetic data obtained. The generated model consists of 10,720 information blocks, each with dimensions of 5×5 m (Figure 17). The model's fine resolution ensures that even minor variations in magnetic susceptibility are recorded, which is crucial for detecting small-scale features or gradual compositional changes. This level of detail supports the identification of both large magnetic bodies and smaller, localized anomalies that may otherwise be overlooked in lower-resolution models. For its part, the uniform grid structure facilitates seamless spatial interpolation, providing a continuous view of the susceptibility distribution that helps to reveal patterns and trends in the subsurface.

Figure 17. 3D magnetic susceptibility block model (CRS: WGS84 35N).

The advanced inversion technique applied here transforms the total magnetic field data into a more interpretable format where susceptibility values directly correlate with the concentration and composition of magnetic materials. This conversion helps clearly delineate boundaries, supporting targeted exploration and resource management within specific zones.

The magnetic inversion, performed in OASIS Montaj using the VOXI module, achieved an exceptional fit between the observed and forward-modelled magnetic anomalies after 11 iterations. The fit metric (DataFit) improved significantly, decreasing from 543.98 to 1.0201, with optimal regularization (RegScal).

Figure 18 illustrates the results of this inversion: (a) the measured magnetic anomalies, (b) the forward-modelled magnetic field derived from the inversion, and (c) the residual map (measured forward), which highlights localized discrepancies. The calculated RMS

value of 5.88 further confirms the strong agreement between the observed and predicted data. These results demonstrate the model’s ability to faithfully represent the subsurface magnetic susceptibility in the study area.

Figure 18. Comparison of measured and forward-modelled magnetic anomalies and their residuals. (a) Measured magnetic anomalies (nT) from UAV data. (b) Forward-modelled magnetic anomalies (nT) derived from the 3D magnetic susceptibility inversion. (c) Residual magnetic field map.

The following images (Figures 19 and 20) present various views of the generated 3D magnetic susceptibility model.

Figure 19. 3D magnetic susceptibility model with orthoimage (CRS: ETRS84 35N).

Figure 20. 3D magnetic susceptibility model with orthoimage (CRS: ETRS84 35N).

The 3D model generated from the magnetic susceptibility parameter has facilitated the geophysical characterization of the repository, providing a detailed depiction of its configuration (Figure 21). In terms of material composition, it has been interpreted that high susceptibility values correlate with a greater proportion of ferromagnetic materials, such as iron and nickel. Conversely, low and negative susceptibility values are associated with areas containing a higher proportion of materials with low ferromagnetic content, including diamagnetic substances such as lead, arsenic, cadmium, and zinc.

Figure 21. 3D model of magnetic susceptibility: (a) High magnetic susceptibility values; (b) Close to zero or negative magnetic susceptibility values.

5. Conclusions

The geophysical survey conducted through aerial magnetometry in the Lavrion repository has yielded significant insights into the repository's geological composition and material distribution.

The acquisition of magnetic field data using the CERBERUS drone has proven to be a highly efficient and simple methodology, as long as a team of geospatial and geophysics experts is available. This technique allows the mapping of large tracts of land in a short period of time, as well as measurements in areas inaccessible to humans due to abrupt topography, dense vegetation, or the presence of environmental hazards, such as in the case of contaminated areas or repositories with health risks.

The analysis of the total magnetic field and its reduction to the pole revealed notable variations in the repository materials, indicating the presence of compositionally distinct areas. Furthermore, the application of the TILT derivative complemented the findings from the Magnetic Field Reduction to the Pole (MFRP) technique, effectively highlighting linear contact zones between bodies of differing magnetic properties. This filter demonstrated numerous linear contacts indicative of diverse material compositions based on their magnetic susceptibility. Additionally, the implementation of the pseudo-gravity algorithm facilitated the identification of the regions with the highest-density materials within the repository.

The development of a 3D model from magnetic susceptibility data further enhanced the geophysical characterization, illustrating a comprehensive overview of the repository's

structure. Notably, areas exhibiting high susceptibility values correlated with increased concentrations of ferromagnetic materials such as iron and nickel, while low and negative susceptibility values were associated with materials containing lower proportions of ferromagnetic and diamagnetic elements, including lead, arsenic, cadmium, and zinc. The average magnetic susceptibility of the repository reflects the values of the geological formations deposited there. The presence of specific elements causes variations in this value, either increasing or decreasing it, which means that the interpretation should be relative rather than absolute.

Overall, the aerial magnetometry survey conducted at the Lavrion repository has provided extensive information on the spatial distribution and composition of materials, achieved through a completely non-invasive methodology, underscoring the effectiveness of drone-based magnetometry in geophysical studies.

These additional conclusions reinforce the role of aerial magnetometry as a versatile, effective tool in geophysical surveys, providing a foundation for further exploration and research in both accessible and challenging environments.

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